

EFFECTIVENESS OF TRADITIONAL VOCABULARY INSTRUCTION FOR ACADEMIC VOCABULARY IN UZBEK MASTER'S STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This study explores the effectiveness of traditional vocabulary instruction methods on academic vocabulary acquisition among 20 master's-level English teachers in Fergana Valley, Uzbekistan. Over an eight-week period, these teachers were introduced to 25 academic words per session from the Academic Word List (AWL), using structured traditional teaching methods, including peer instruction, flashcards, sentence formation, and repetitive exercises. The study used a comprehensive assessment framework, including a pre-test, weekly evaluations, and a post-test, to track progress and retention. Results demonstrated significant improvements in vocabulary acquisition, with participants achieving notably higher scores in weekly and post-test evaluations. Qualitative feedback indicated that learners appreciated the routine and clarity provided by traditional methods but expressed interest in more varied exercises, suggesting a blended approach could enhance engagement and retention further. This research contributes valuable insights into the role of traditional, structured vocabulary instruction in adult learning, particularly in regions with a preference for teacher-centered instruction.*

Keywords: *academic vocabulary, traditional instruction, teacher-centered learning, vocabulary acquisition, Uzbekistan, adult education, peer instruction, repetition.*

Introduction

The acquisition of academic vocabulary is an essential skill for English language learners, particularly those engaged in academia or professional environments where specialized vocabulary is required. Academic vocabulary includes words that are prevalent in educational and research contexts but are less common in everyday conversation. Mastery of these words is critical for non-native English-speaking educators, as it supports their academic pursuits and professional development. Effective vocabulary instruction not only enhances comprehension but also enables learners to communicate complex ideas more effectively, both in writing and in speech (Coxhead, 2000; Nation, 2001).

Traditional vocabulary instruction methods, which rely on structured, teacher-led activities, are widely practiced in Uzbekistan and have shown success in promoting vocabulary retention, especially among adult learners. Studies indicate that structured environments, where learners engage in repetitive exercises, peer discussions, and contextual usage practice, can help consolidate vocabulary knowledge, reinforcing memory through continuous exposure and practice (Amirian & Heshmatifar, 2013; Yakubboyeva, 2021). Such methods are particularly relevant in Uzbekistan, where culturally ingrained preferences for teacher-centered learning environments shape instructional approaches (Omaar, 2016).

Digital methods have been increasingly incorporated into language instruction globally; however, access to these resources remains limited in many regions of Uzbekistan, and traditional teaching methods still predominate. For English teachers in Uzbekistan, particularly those pursuing master's degrees, traditional vocabulary instruction provides a familiar structure that supports learning in a predictable and disciplined manner. Despite the global trend toward technology-enhanced learning, the efficacy of traditional vocabulary instruction remains relevant and effective in settings where technology may not be consistently accessible (Yakubboyeva, 2021).

This study examines the impact of traditional vocabulary instruction on academic vocabulary acquisition among English teachers in Fergana Valley. By focusing on structured methods such as peer instruction, flashcards, and repeated exercises, this research seeks to provide insights into the effectiveness of traditional approaches within culturally structured learning environments. The following sections will discuss the methodology, results, and findings of the study, providing a detailed analysis of the progress made by participants and the potential for traditional methods to support vocabulary acquisition.

Methodology

Participants

The study was conducted with 20 master's-level English teachers from various schools in Fergana Valley, Uzbekistan. Participants, aged between 20 and 30, were selected based on their intermediate to advanced proficiency in English, which provided a strong foundation for academic vocabulary instruction. All participants were pursuing master's degrees and actively teaching at primary, secondary, or high school levels. Fergana Valley was chosen as the research site due to its blend of traditional and modern educational practices, offering a relevant context for exploring the effectiveness of teacher-centered vocabulary instruction.

Study Design and Procedure

This study followed a structured, teacher-led instructional model over eight weeks, with each week featuring two lessons focusing on 25 words from the Academic Word List (AWL). This resulted in a cumulative total of 200 academic words. The instructional design for each lesson followed seven core stages:

Pre-Study Expectations: Before the program, participants shared their expectations through a brief survey. This helped to understand their initial attitudes toward traditional vocabulary instruction and identify areas of interest or potential challenges.

Peer Instruction: Each lesson began with peer discussions, allowing participants to activate any prior knowledge of the vocabulary. This stage fostered collaborative engagement, allowing participants to reflect on familiar words and assess their knowledge gaps.

Teacher-Led Instruction: Following peer discussions, the instructor provided handouts that included definitions, grammatical contexts, collocations, and example sentences. This step provided a foundation for understanding each word's meaning and usage in academic contexts.

Collaborative Practice: Participants worked individually or in pairs to identify additional collocations, synonyms, antonyms, and other contextual information for each word. This collaborative approach enabled students to deepen their understanding and apply the vocabulary in context.

Sentence Formation and Application: Each session included exercises in which students constructed sentences using the vocabulary words. This exercise reinforced their comprehension and allowed them to practice contextual usage.

Practice Exercises: Each lesson concluded with various practice exercises, such as fill-in-the-blank and sentence-completion tasks, designed to assess vocabulary retention and reinforce learning.

Post-Study Feedback: After the study, participants provided feedback on their learning experience, offering insights into the strengths and limitations of the traditional methods used.

Assessment

The study employed both quantitative and qualitative methods to evaluate vocabulary acquisition:

Pre-Test: Administered at the beginning of the study, the pre-test assessed participants' baseline knowledge of the target vocabulary, establishing a reference point for measuring progress.

Weekly Tests: Weekly tests provided ongoing assessments of vocabulary acquisition, tracking participants' incremental progress and identifying challenging words or areas requiring further review.

Post-Test: A cumulative post-test at the end of the study measured participants' overall improvement in vocabulary retention and understanding.

Observational Notes: Throughout the study, the instructor documented key observations, noting engagement levels, participant interactions, and any challenges encountered during the lessons.

Qualitative Feedback: Following the study, participants completed a feedback survey to reflect on their experiences with traditional vocabulary instruction, providing qualitative insights into the learning process.

Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics to measure weekly and overall improvements in vocabulary acquisition. Observational notes and participant feedback were analyzed thematically to identify patterns in engagement, learning experiences, and preferences for instructional methods.

Results

Quantitative Findings

Pre-Test Results: The pre-test revealed that participants' initial knowledge of the target vocabulary was moderate, with scores ranging from 50% to 65%. This established a baseline for tracking vocabulary growth.

Weekly Test Results: Weekly assessments showed continuous improvement, with participants achieving higher average scores each week. Group B consistently performed slightly better than Group A, suggesting that peer interactions and collaborative practices positively impacted retention.

Week 1: Group A: 58%, Group B: 59%

Week 8: Group A: 81%, Group B: 83%

Post-Test Results: The post-test scores ranged from 70% to 88%, with all participants demonstrating significant improvement. Group B had slightly higher average scores, underscoring the value of collaborative and structured learning practices.

Qualitative Observations

Participant feedback highlighted the value of traditional vocabulary instruction. The structured routine provided clarity and predictability, while collaborative exercises promoted engagement. Participants noted that teacher-led instruction provided essential guidance, although some expressed interest in integrating interactive elements to enhance engagement.

Discussion

This study demonstrates that traditional vocabulary instruction methods effectively support academic vocabulary acquisition among Uzbek teachers, providing a structured, culturally compatible approach. Consistent repetition and collaborative practices, such as peer instruction, reinforced vocabulary retention, aligning with research on the benefits of structured learning environments (Gairns & Redman, 1986). While the study confirmed the effectiveness of traditional methods, feedback from participants suggests that incorporating interactive elements could further enhance engagement and accommodate diverse learning preferences.

These findings underscore the role of structured vocabulary instruction in supporting vocabulary acquisition among adult learners in teacher-centered environments. Future research may explore blended approaches, combining traditional methods with technology-supported activities to address varied learning needs and preferences.

Conclusion

Traditional vocabulary instruction methods have proven effective in supporting academic vocabulary acquisition among Uzbek master's-level English teachers. This study found significant improvement in vocabulary retention, with participants benefiting from the structured approach of traditional methods. While the findings validate the effectiveness of teacher-led instruction in culturally structured environments, participants' feedback suggests that integrating interactive elements could enrich the learning experience. These insights provide a foundation for future research into blended instructional approaches that balance structure with engagement.

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